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**STUDY OF AUTONOMY AND SELF- RELIANCE IN RELATION TO DECISION
MAKING AND CAPACITY BUILDING OF ADOLESCENT GIRLS**

Education

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Abstract

This study is an attempt to find out the relationship of autonomy and self reliance with the two prominent dimensions (decision making and capacity building) of empowerment of adolescent girls studying in government and non-government senior secondary schools. A sample of 150 girls studying at senior secondary schools aged 16 to 18 years were selected randomly from rural and urban areas of Rohtak dist., Haryana state. 'Adolescent girls empowerment scale' developed by Dr. Devendra Singh Sisodia and Dr. AlpanaSingh was used as measuring instruments. The data was analysed by using t-ratio. The findings of the study were that the autonomy and self-reliance is positively correlated with decision making and capacity building.

Introduction

Women are traditionally less involved in decision making of all levels. Their important role is not recognized and therefore still not accepted in decision making. Females and children are often considered the most vulnerable members in societies, based on their typical lack of access to essential resources such as funds, social power, property and information, in addition to their differences in physical strength and childbearing capacity (Enarson 2000; Enarson and

Fordham 2001; Jabry 2005; Peek 2008). *Femals are the integral part of family & vital force in socio-economic progress. Her progress is one of the important part of changing world.* Since the older times, women have been treated as second rate citizens of all across the globe. The situation is almost the same everywhere-irrespective of the developed country or the developing country-caste, community, colour or creed a position which is comparable in many ways, with that of racial minorities. Women have been relegated to secondary position despite the fact that they numerically constitute about half the world population today.

One of the most important tasks for all adolescent girls is learning the skills that will help them manage their own lives and make positive, healthy choices. Parents and others can help youth develop this sense of self-governance, responsibility, independence, and decision-making, which are together called autonomy. Autonomy is a crucial developmental task of adolescence, namely because it is closely linked to individuation and identity formation (Blos, 1967; Steinberg & Silverberg, 1986; Ryan & Lynch, 1989; Smetana & Asquish, 1994). Autonomy refers to an adolescent's growing ability to think, feel, make decisions, and act on her or his own. The development of autonomy does not end after the teen years. Throughout adulthood, autonomy continues to develop whenever someone is challenged to act with a new level of self-reliance. The growth of independence is certainly a crucial component of becoming autonomous, but autonomy means more than just behaving independently. Autonomy has special meaning during the preteen and teen years because it signifies that an adolescent is a unique, capable, independent person who depends less on parents and other adults. The perception of autonomy by the adolescent is associated with behaviours that are important to modulate the level of success of transition to adulthood and home leaving (Benaches, 1981; Williamson & Campbell, 1985; Anderson & Anderson, 1986). Though today's women take decision effectively, there is need of changing former thinking style of whole world. Freedom of few women is not for all women. Decision making process is generally influenced by the level of knowledge. It can be regarded as the mental processes (cognitive process) resulting in the selection of a course of action among several alternative scenarios. Every decision making process produces a final

choice. The output can be an action or an opinion of choice. *Some powers are by birth but some abilities can develop by certain effort & trying. Improving individuals abilities to solve problems and make decisions is recognized as an important issue in education, industry, and government.*

Women's participation in decision-making was assessed through three measures: involvement in decisions on woman's own health care, involvement in decisions on major household purchases, and involvement in decisions on visits to family or relatives. Without active participation of women & incorporation of women's perspectives at all levels of decision making, the goals of equality development and peace cannot be achieved. It is only possible that time when women start using their inner qualities and abilities like decision making from their adolescence stage. Because today's adolescents (girls) are tomorrow's adults (women). Capacity and capability building is defined as the empowerment which encompasses the ability, will and skills to initiate, plan, manage, undertake, organise, budget, monitor/supervise and evaluate project activities. Thus capacity and capability building are related to the organizational and functional levels as well as to individuals, groups and institutions. It was reported that late adolescents achieve a higher degree of autonomy regarding the choice of friends and occupation, of management of their own money, and of physical activities performed outside the family home (Douvan & Adelson, 1966; Bosma et al. 1996). They also depict higher abilities for social integration (Greenberger, 1984), participating in a larger number of peer and adult-oriented activities (Silverberg & Steinberg, 1987). The present study is an effort to see that, how autonomy and self-reliance is correlated with decision making ability and capacity building among adolescent girls.

OBJECTIVES

1. To study the relationship of autonomy and self-reliance with decision-making ability of adolescent girls studying in government and non-government schools.
2. To study the relationship of autonomy and self-reliance with capacity building ability of adolescent girls studying in government and non-government schools.

HYPOTHESES

1. There is no significant relationship between autonomy and self-reliance with decision-making ability of adolescent girls studying in government and non-government schools.
2. There is no significant relationship between autonomy and self-reliance with capacity building ability of adolescent girls studying in government and non-government schools.

METHODOLOGY

SAMPLE OF THE STUDY

Sample of the present study consisted of 150 adolescent girls of the age group 16 to 18 years, studying in Senior Secondary Schools, selected randomly from six Schools of District Rohtak, Haryana (80 girls from government schools and 70 from non-government schools).

TOOLS

Following scales have been used to collect the data related to Adolescent Girls' Empowerment and Socio- Economic Status :

1. For assessing the adolescent girls empowerment, 'Adolescent Girls' Empowerment Scale' developed by Dr. Devender Singh Sisodia and Dr. Alpana Singh has been used by the investigator.

PROCEDURE

Descriptive survey method of research was employed for the present study. The tools employed in the study were administered on the secondary school students of the age group 16 to 18 years.

Table 1: Showing the value of correlation between autonomy and self-reliance with decision-making among adolescent girls studying in Non-Government and Government Schools.

Schools	Dimension	N	r	Level of Significance 0.05
Non-Government	Autonomy and Self-reliance	70	0.21	Not Sig
	Decision making			
Government	Autonomy and Self-reliance	80	0.31	Sig
	Decision making			

In reference to the adolescent girls studying in non- government schools the coefficient of correlation of autonomy and self-reliance with decision making is 0.21. It is inferred that in this case autonomy and self-reliance is positively correlated with decision making ability but this correlation is not significant at 0.05 level of significance.

The coefficient of correlations of autonomy and self-reliance with decision making of girls studying in government schools, table shows positive correlation (0.31) and also significant at 0.05 level of significance.

Table 2: Showing the value of Correlation between autonomy and self-reliance with capacity building among adolescent girls studying in Non-Government and Government Schools

Schools	Dimension	N	r	Level of Sig at .05
Non-Government	Autonomy and Self-reliance	70	0.42	Sig.
	Capacity Building			
Government	Autonomy and Self-reliance	80	0.03	Not Sig.
	Capacity Building			

Table 2 shows that autonomy and self-reliance of adolescent girls studying in non-government schools is significantly positively correlated with capacity building having correlation coefficient, 0.42.

Further it has been explored that autonomy and self-reliance of adolescent girls studying in government schools is also positively correlated with capacity building but it is not significant.

CONCLUSION

From the results given above, it can be concluded that in case of adolescent girls studying in non-government schools, autonomy and self-reliance is positively correlated with decision making ability but not significant but it is significantly positively correlated with capacity building. Capacity building means capacity to undertake economic, social and political activities

like ability to manage productive resources, ability to interact effectively in public sphere, agreeing on common issues etc. Results reveals that in case of non-government school girls who have high level of autonomy and self-reliance are also capable to manage economic, social and political issues in their lifes.

In case of adolescent girls studying in government schools, it can be stated that autonomy and self-reliance is positively correlated with decision making and Capacity Building ability but it is signifecantly correlated with decision making ability and not significantly correlatedwith capacity building.

REFERENCES

- Anderson, W. W., & Anderson, D. D. (1986). Thai Muslim adolescents' self, sexuality, and autonomy. *Ethos*, 14, 368-394.
- Benaches, J. L. (1981). Autonomy as a dimension of social integration of 15 years old adolescent (in Spanish). *Psicologica*, 2, 167-177.
- Blos, P. (1967). The second individuation process of adolescence. *Psychoanalytic Study of the Child*, 22, 162-186.
- Bosma, H.A., Jackson, S.E., Zijsling, D.H., Cicognani E., Xerri, M.L., Honesss, Charman, L. (1996). Who as the final say? Decisions on adolescent behaviour within the family. *Journal of Adolescence*, 19, 277-291.
- Douvan, E., Adelson, J. (1966) *The adolescent experience*, New York, J. Wiley & Sons.
- Enarson, Elaine (1999). "Through Women's Eyes: A Gendered Research Agenda for Disaster Social Science. *Disasters* 22(2): 157-173.
- Enarson, Elaine and Maureen Fordham (2001). "From Women's Needs to Women's Rights in Disasters. *Environmental Hazards* 3: 133-136.
- Greenberger, E. (1984). Defining psycho-social maturity in adolescence, in Karoly& Steffen (ed.) *Adolescence behaviour disorders: Foundations and contemporary concerns*, vol.III. Lexington Books.
- Hanna, K. M., & Guthrie, D. (2003). Adolescents' behavioural autonomy related to diabetes

- management and adolescent activities/rules. *Diabetes Education*, 29, 283-291.
- Jabry, Amer (2005). *After the Cameras Have Gone: Children in Disasters*. Report prepared for Plan London: Design2Print Solutions Ltd.
- Peek, Lori. (2008). "Children and Disasters: Understanding Vulnerability, Developing Capacities and Promoting Resilience – An Introduction. *Children, Youth and Environments* 18(1): 1-29. Available from: <http://www.colorado.edu/journals/cye>.
- Pinto, K. C. (2004). Intersections of gender and age in health care: adapting autonomy and confidentiality for the adolescent girl. *Qualitative Health Research*, 14, 78-99.
- Poole, M. E., Cooney, G. H., & Cheong, A. C. S. (1986). Adolescent perceptions of family cohesiveness, autonomy and independence in Australia and Singapore. *Comparative Family Studies*, 17, 311-332.
- Ryan, R. M., & Lynch, J. H. (1989) Emotional autonomy versus detachment: revisiting the vicissitudes of adolescence and young adulthood. *Child Development*, 60, 340-356.
- Smetana, J. G., & Asquith, P. (1994) Adolescents' and parents' conceptions of parental authority and personal autonomy. *Child Development*, 65, 1147-1162.
- Steinberg, L., & Silverberg, S. B. (1986). The vicissitudes of autonomy in early adolescence. *Child Development*, 57, 841-851.
- Williamson, J. A., & Campbell, L. P. (1985). Parents and their children comment of adolescence. *Adolescence*, 20, 745-748.